

Data Infrastructure

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the data infrastructure setup used to store, manage and process the smart meter data delivered by Radius in the project. The infrastructure is designed to ensure reliable, reproducible, and scalable handling of large volumes of time-series and raw measurement data, forming a foundation for later analytics and data pipeline development. The main components include a Postgres Database for structured, relational data access, object storage for timeseries parquet files, and an Airflow-based ingest adapter integrated to support both operational queries and batch processing during prototyping. These components are aligned with the data model described in the data specification document (D2.1 [1]).

The initial prototyping uses local file storage while remaining compatible with other data governance platforms such as EDDK and INILAB infrastructure. This design ensures that the data management workflow is traceable and compliant with the requirements of the Danish energy sector. It further ensures that the platform can integrate additional datasets or migrate ingestion sources with ease, given different infrastructure deployments. Future work based on this deliverable includes improvements to partitioning strategies, ingestion capabilities, and long-term data governance measures, which will evolve the platform into a scalable, hybrid architecture that supports extensive analytics and pipeline-based services as the project advances. Most of these results are presented in D4.1 [2].

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1 Introduction

1.1 About the project

The rapid electrification of the grid is placing more pressure on distribution networks, where increasing numbers of heat pumps, electric vehicles (EVs), and other power-electronic devices introduce additional loads and often severe phase imbalance. At the same time, DSOs generally lack detailed observability of low-voltage (LV) grids: topology records are incomplete, phase-connection information is often inaccurate, and power-quality monitoring is limited or absent at secondary substations. This lack of granular, per-phase visibility forces DSOs to rely on conservative planning assumptions, leading to unnecessary capacity buffers, delayed customer connections, and costly reinforcement measures that slow down the green transition.

Motivated by these challenges, the 3PhaseInsight project seeks to unlock the value of per-phase smart-meter measurements from around 100,000 customers by developing advanced analytics and scalable data-processing pipelines. The central idea is that reconfigured smart meters can provide per-phase voltage, power, and harmonic information at a granularity that enables a new level of LV situational awareness. From this data, the project explores what insights can be obtained through state-of-the-art data-driven and machine-learning algorithms, and how these insights can support more efficient operation, planning, and stakeholder-level data sharing.

The project focuses on developing and validating a suite of “data apps” including per-phase topology correction, imbalance screening, and detection of significant electrification loads, such as heat pumps and EV chargers. These analytics are integrated into an open-source, cloud-deployable data-pipeline framework that supports scalable execution, modular workflow composition, and interoperability with DSO environments. By combining improved LV observability with replicable digital tools, the project aims to help DSOs target interventions more precisely, design new customer-facing services, and establish a pathway for broader sector adoption and future expansion of the analytics toolbox.

1.2 Purpose of this document

The goal of this deliverable is to describe the infrastructure set up to store, manage, and process the data delivered by Radius. This includes the database system used for topology and other relational data, the storage layer for the timeseries data, and the orchestration layer that ensures a consistent and reproducible data flow. This provides a common understanding of the components involved in data management and also supports discussions on architecture, performance, and scalability, while also serving as a reference for further extensions and integration work.

1.3 Scope

This deliverable covers the data infrastructures used in this project to handle the data described in D2.1 [1]. This includes hosting the data in Energydata.dk (EDDK) Platform, a description of the Local prototyping environment used in D3.1 [3] and D3.2 [4], and the final Platform Infrastructure for deployment. The described infrastructure is tailored to the currently available radial grid dataset. It covers the database, object storage, and ingestion pipeline used to handle the CSV source files delivered by Radius.

2 Energidata.dk data host

Energidata.dk (EDDK) is a national platform for storing and sharing energy-related datasets in Denmark hosted and maintained by DTU Wind. It is operated to ensure that research and industry partners have secure, compliant, and controlled access to energy data. The platform fulfils the following features:

- **Compliance and security:** EDDK fulfils all the legal requirements for storing sensitive energy data, including GDPR and Danish energy sector regulations.
- **Access model:** Datasets are typically made available through APIs or secure storage endpoints, enabling controlled distribution to authorised partners.
- **Integration potential:** In projects such as ours, EDDK can serve as the authoritative storage for the original Radius source files. While the prototyping phase relies on local file storage, the ingest adapter (Airflow) can be configured to fetch files directly from EDDK once datasets are published there.
- **Advantages:** Using EDDK ensures data traceability, reduces duplication of storage responsibility, and aligns the project with the broader data governance framework of the Danish energy sector.

2.1 Scale of the Challenge

The Radius smart meter dataset spans a large number of metering points across dozens of postal codes in Denmark. Each meter records multiple electrical quantities across three phases, at 15-minute resolution. This translates to 21 individual datastreams per meter, yielding a very high total count of datastreams. Making a dataset of such magnitude available in a structured, searchable, and manageable way on EDDK was a significant engineering challenge that required careful planning of the dataset topology, metadata design, and upload strategy.

2.2 Dataset Design and Partitioning Strategy

EDDK imposes a practical limit of approximately 12 200 datastreams per dataset. While this limit exists primarily for performance and usability reasons, it also aligns with good data management practice: a single monolithic dataset containing hundreds of thousands of datastreams would be unwieldy to navigate, slow to query, and impractical for most downstream use cases. EDDK's export functionality allows users to select which datasets to include in an export, so splitting the data into logically coherent subsets preserves full flexibility while keeping each dataset manageable.

The data was therefore partitioned using two complementary strategies:

1. **By postal code:** The first set of datasets groups all meters within a single anonymized postal code into one dataset, named with the convention `DK-0001` (e.g. `DK-0010`, `DK-0018`). This division covers 17 postal codes (see Table 1).
2. **By transformer ID (first two digits):** For postal codes where the number of datastreams exceeds the platform limit, datasets are further subdivided based on the first two digits of the Transformer ID. For example, a dataset such as `DK_0018_10-14` includes only transformers starting with the digits 10 through 14. This scheme was applied to 15 additional postal codes (see Table 2 for an example).

The mapping from each meter to its transformer and postal code was derived from topology metadata files that associate every metering point with its anonymised postal code, Transformer ID, Feeder ID, and Cabinet ID.

Table 1: Datasets on EDDK divided by postal code geographic grouping

Postal Code	Ingested	Published to EDDK	Dataset created	Datastreams	From	To
DK-0001	Yes	Yes	Yes	1533	09/10/2023 02.00	22/05/2024 10.45
DK-0002	Yes	Yes	Yes	1638	06/11/2023 09.15	15/05/2024 22.45
DK-0003	Yes	Yes	Yes	3927	06/11/2023 09.00	15/05/2024 22.45
DK-0004	Yes	Yes	Yes	3675	06/11/2023 09.00	21/05/2024 04.45
DK-0005	Yes	Yes	Yes	4935	21/11/2023 07.00	22/05/2024 04.45
DK-0006	Yes	Yes	Yes	4788	21/11/2023 07.00	22/05/2024 04.45
DK-0007	Yes	Yes	Yes	5250	09/10/2023 02.00	22/05/2024 04.45
DK-0008	Yes	Yes	Yes	5355	06/11/2023 09.00	15/05/2024 22.45
DK-0009	Yes	Yes	Yes	7812	09/10/2023 02.00	15/05/2024 22.45
DK-0010	Yes	Yes	Yes	8988	06/11/2023 09.00	21/05/2024 04.45
DK-0011	Yes	Yes	Yes	9870	06/11/2023 09.00	15/05/2024 22.00
DK-0012	Yes	Yes	Yes	10290	06/11/2023 09.00	22/05/2024 04.45
DK-0013	Yes	Yes	Yes	10689	09/10/2023 02.00	20/05/2024 07.45
DK-0014	Yes	Yes	Yes	11550	09/10/2023 02.00	22/05/2024 04.45
DK-0015	Yes	Yes	Yes	11571	09/10/2023 02.00	21/05/2024 04.15
DK-0016	Yes	Yes	Yes	11949	06/11/2023 09.00	22/05/2024 04.45
DK-0017	Yes	Yes	Yes	12243	06/11/2023 09.00	22/05/2024 04.45

Table 2: Example of a geographical group divided into datasets by transformer ID

Postal Code	Dataset	Ingested	Published to EDDK	Dataset created	Datastreams	From	To
DK-0018	DK-0018_10-14	Yes	Yes	Yes	11634	18/09/2023 07.00.00	15/05/2024 22.45.00
	DK-0018_15-19	Yes	Yes	Yes	9996	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 10.45.00
	DK-0018_21-29	Yes	Yes	Yes	10332	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 04.45.00
	DK-0018_29-33	Yes	Yes	Yes	10269	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 04.45.00
	DK-0018_35-35	Yes	Yes	Yes	7413	18/09/2023 07.00.00	21/05/2024 10.45.00
	DK-0018_37-44	Yes	Yes	Yes	10437	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 04.45.00
	DK-0018_45-47	Yes	Yes	Yes	10605	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 04.45.00
	DK-0018_48-54	Yes	Yes	Yes	11613	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 10.45.00
	DK-0018_56-59	Yes	Yes	Yes	10899	18/09/2023 07.00.00	21/05/2024 10.45.00
	DK-0018_60-66	Yes	Yes	Yes	9345	18/09/2023 07.30.00	22/05/2024 02.15.00
	DK-0018_66-69	Yes	Yes	Yes	11130	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 04.45.00
	DK-0018_70-72	Yes	Yes	Yes	9639	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 04.45.00
	DK-0018_72-78	Yes	Yes	Yes	10416	18/09/2023 07.00.00	15/05/2024 20.00.00
	DK-0018_78-83	Yes	Yes	Yes	11634	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 04.45.00
	DK-0018_84-91	Yes	Yes	Yes	11004	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 04.45.00
DK-0018_92-95	Yes	Yes	Yes	11340	18/09/2023 07.00.00	15/05/2024 22.45.00	
DK-0018_97-98	Yes	Yes	Yes	8694	18/09/2023 07.00.00	22/05/2024 04.45.00	

2.3 Datastream Properties and Metadata

Each datastream published on EDDK carries a rich set of metadata properties, enabling filtering and discovery across the platform. The common properties shared by all datasets are divided into the following categories:

- **Network & Infrastructure:** Cabinet ID, Delivery point ID, LV feeder, Service Fuse Size (A), Phase, Topology processing level.
- **Metering & Data Quality:** Meter ID, Measured quantity, Unit, Time resolution, First measurement, Last measurement, Processing level, Scaling, Significant figures.
- **Site & Geographic Details:** Geo tag (anonymized postal code), Location, Has heat pump, Has solar panel.
- **Administrative & Metadata Management:** GDPR classification, Data license, Organization, CKAN references, Project tag, Theme tag, Comment, Years covered.

Datasets partitioned by transformer ID include one additional property — **Transformer ID** — which allows direct linkage of measurements to specific grid assets. This property is particularly useful for grid-level analyses and for filtering datastreams belonging to a particular transformer. Datastream names follow the convention *metric_phase_meterID_resolution* (e.g. *active_power_p14_l1_110703_15min*), and each stream is registered with the MQTT topic pattern *meterID/metric/phase/resolution*.

The dataset *3PhaseInsight – Project* serves as the primary entry point on the EDDK platform. It contains a link to a central spreadsheet which provides a comprehensive overview of the available

datasets through multiple informative tabs. This spreadsheet documents all dataset inventories, covering postal-code groupings, transformer associations, and detailed datastream counts. The workbook is structured as follows: the first tab lists all datasets grouped by postal code along with their ingestion and publication status; the second tab provides a detailed breakdown of each postal-code dataset; the third tab lists datasets grouped by transformer ID; and subsequent tabs break down each transformer-based dataset by the specific transformers it includes and the associated datastream metrics.

2.4 Data Processing and Upload Workflow

The pipeline that transforms raw data files into published EDDK datastreams operates in the following stages:

- 1. Parquet ingestion via DuckDB:** The source data is stored as wide-format Parquet files (e.g. `feeder_539243.parquet`). A single Parquet file may contain data for multiple postal codes. Therefore, the ingestion framework uses configuration files to fetch and filter only the specific feeders required for a particular dataset. DuckDB's vectorised query engine reads these files and performs an UNPIVOT (wide-to-tall) transformation in-memory. Column names are parsed to extract the metric, phase, and meter ID, which are then composed into a topic string of the form `meterID/metric/phase/resolution`. The time resolution is auto-detected by computing the most common interval. A one-hour backward shift is applied to all timestamps to convert from end-of-interval to start-of-interval representation in UTC.
- 2. Intermediate storage in TimescaleDB:** The tall-schema rows (`ts, topic, dtype, value`) are bulk-loaded into hypertables via binary COPY, with deduplication handled by an `ON CONFLICT` clause. Each dataset subset maps to a dedicated table.
- 3. MQTT streaming to EDDK:** Rather than batch-uploading static files, the publication step streams each row as an individual MQTT message to the EDDK broker over TLS. Streaming was chosen over batch upload due to the very high number of datastreams; it allows each message to be independently timestamped and routed to the correct datastream topic. Each message carries a JSON payload of the form `{“timestamp”: epoch_ms, “value”: float}` and is published with QoS 1 (at-least-once delivery).
- 4. Orchestration & Progress Tracking:** A Python-based orchestrator manages parallel workers, each responsible for one dataset subset. Workers follow the sequence: ingest Parquet → publish to MQTT → mark complete. By keeping track of the offset in TimescaleDB and maintaining filesystem-based progress markers for ingested Parquet files, the pipeline is robust and can resume cleanly after interruptions. Resource gating ensures disk and RAM thresholds are respected.

2.5 Summary

Publishing the 3PhaseInsight smart meter data on EDDK demonstrated both the capability of the platform and the importance of thoughtful dataset design when dealing with very large-scale metering data. By partitioning the data into logically coherent subsets — by anonymized postal code and by transformer ID — the project ensured that each dataset remains within the platform's practical limits while preserving full flexibility for data consumers through EDDK's multi-dataset export functionality. The combination of DuckDB-based vectorised processing for data transformation, TimescaleDB for intermediate staging, and MQTT streaming for publication proved to be an effective architecture for handling this volume of data on a single server. All dataset inventories, metadata, and structural information are consolidated in the accompanying Excel workbook, providing a comprehensive reference for anyone accessing the data on EDDK.

3 Local prototyping environment

Before implementing the cloud-compatible platform, a local prototyping environment was created. Here, the source data, previously stored in CSVs for each month, each containing one month of data for all smart meters, is converted into per-smart-meter Apache Parquet files for the entire period.

This has two purposes. First, the switch from CSV to Parquet improves storage and computational efficiency. Parquet's columnar format allows analyses to read only the relevant fields (e.g., timestamp and consumption) without scanning entire rows, while its compression and encoding schemes substantially reduce file size compared to plain text CSV, in this case by a factor of 5. This format also integrates well with Apache Airflow, which is used in later data infrastructure.

Second, organising the data per meter rather than per month aligns the file structure with the typical unit of analysis. Retrieving a single meter's full history no longer requires scanning all nine source files and filtering by meter ID; instead, it requires reading one small, pre-sorted file. This eliminates temporal fragmentation, simplifies time-series operations such as resampling and gap detection, and enables independent, parallelizable processing of individual meters.

The prototyping environment allows for a fast and low-overhead development of data apps, where each data app simply was a new folder and associated git repository in the project. Since the raw and processed data was stored in a parallel, structured folder (illustrated in Figure 1), new data apps could be created from a simple python template, which includes configuration-driven execution and composition of data apps.

Figure 1: The prototyping environment uses a primarily folder-based data organisation, as illustrated in the left figure. Data apps and pipelines come with configuration files, thus supporting a basic traceability of run configurations, illustrated on the right.

Whereas the prototyping environment is well-suited for development of new data app concepts, it is not suitable for a production environment with stricter data governance, updating input-data and larger datasets. Since any data corrections lead to creation of full copies of the original data, it is also not storage-space efficient.

4 Platform Infrastructure Components

This section provides an overview of the data infrastructure components that enable storage, access and processing of smart meter datasets for a cloud-compatible platform. The architecture combines topology and metadata storage in a PostgreSQL database, raw and intermediate file storage in an object storage, and a flexible Airflow-based ingest adapter that orchestrates data flows from source files into the database. A combination of these components forms a modular and future-proof setup that supports both prototyping and scalable processing needs. As shown in Figure 2, the infrastructure is designed to accommodate current local file ingestion while remaining compatible with secure external sources, such as energydata.dk (EDDK). The subsections below briefly describe each component, outlining its role within the infrastructure and how it supports the project data management workflow.

Figure 2: An overview of the data infrastructure architecture

4.1 Data source

The Data Source is not a fixed piece of the Data Infrastructure. It can be implemented on a per use-case basis. For the prototyping phase, this will be just local file storage on the server, but this could just as well be an S3 bucket, an API or any other Data Storage solution.

4.2 PostgreSQL DB

A PostgreSQL instance is used to store all topology data and metadata derived from the Smart Meters and other measurements. PostgreSQL is a mature, open-source relational database that provides robust transactional guarantees and flexible querying over structured data.

- **Use case:** fast querying, aggregation, and analysis of topology and metadata.
- **Schema:** based on the relational data model described in Deliverable D2.1 (Data Specification)[1], with foreign key constraints enforcing referential integrity across related entities.
- **Optimisation:** a deliberate indexing strategy supports complex queries and joins across the topology model. Timeseries measurements are deliberately kept out of the database and stored in object storage instead, avoiding write bottlenecks on the database and leveraging the high-throughput read characteristics of object storage for large-scale measurement access.

4.3 Object Storage

Raw source data, delivered in CSV and converted to Parquet, is stored in an Object Storage Solution. The platform currently supports S3-compatible object storage as well as Azure Blob Storage. An extendable Base Connector lays the foundation for easy integration of additional object storage technologies if required.

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- **Data format:** Parquet files partitioned by date and sharded on the Smart Meter ID. The number of shards can be optimized depending on common query patterns. As a compressed, columnar format with embedded schema and per-column statistics, Parquet reduces storage footprint substantially compared to the source CSVs and lets queries read only the required columns and skip irrelevant row groups entirely (e.g. when filtering on meter ID or time range), rather than scanning whole files.
 - **Derived artifacts:** Besides the raw measurements, the object storage holds the outputs of the data cleaning process as separate, co-partitioned datasets: per-value quality flags recording *why* a measurement was rejected, a sparse corrections dataset containing imputed replacement values, and a compact phase map capturing corrected phase assignments per meter. The raw data itself is never overwritten; instead, the requested processing level (raw, cleaned, or cleaned and phase-corrected) is assembled at read time by overlaying these artifacts, which keeps the storage overhead small (the flag and correction datasets amount to only a few percent of the raw data volume) while preserving a full audit trail from every cleaned value back to its source.
 - **Purpose:** Long-term storage of source data and efficient access for batch processing or ML use cases.
 - **Advantages:** Partitioned and sharded parquet data is very well suited for processing-heavy, parallelized workflows using frameworks like Dask and Pandas. The connector pattern ensures flexibility for targeting different storage technologies if required.

4.4 Dask Cluster

Processing-heavy workloads are executed on a Dask cluster, consisting of a scheduler and a configurable number of workers.

- **Function:** distributed, parallel processing of the partitioned Parquet datasets, e.g. for data cleaning, classification and statistical labeling workloads.
- **Integration:** processing tasks are dispatched to the cluster by the Airflow-orchestrated data apps; computations are expressed lazily and only materialized on the workers, which read the required partitions directly from object storage.
- **Scalability:** the number of workers can be scaled independently of the storage layer, so compute capacity follows the workload rather than the data volume.

4.5 Airflow DAG

Data ingestion is managed via an Apache Airflow DAG, implemented in Python.

- **Function:** reads source CSV files and ingests them into the infrastructure.
- **Current configuration:** the DAG reads CSVs directly from the server's local file system.
- **Flexibility:** the adapter allows for flexibility regarding ingestion from other sources in the future (e.g., S3, FTP, API endpoints), as it can easily be adapted to target a different source.
- **Classification:** the DAG functions as an Ingest Adapter, ensuring reproducible and monitored data ingestion workflows.

4.6 Summary

The infrastructure described above comprises five core components:

- a PostgreSQL database holding topology data and metadata
- an object storage layer holding raw and derived timeseries data as partitioned and sharded Parquet files
- a Dask cluster providing distributed processing of these datasets
- an Airflow-based ingest adapter orchestrating data flows from source files into storage
- a per-use-case data source that is currently local file storage during prototyping

A deliberate separation of concerns underpins the design - structured topology and metadata are queried relationally in PostgreSQL, while high-volume timeseries measurements are kept in object storage, where high-throughput read access can be exploited without bottlenecking the database.

The publication of the 3PhaseInsight dataset on EDDK, implemented by an external partner, follows a separate pipeline and illustrates the importance of thoughtful dataset design when working with very large-scale metering data. Partitioning the data into logically coherent subsets, by postal code and by transformer ID, kept each dataset within the platform's practical limits while preserving full flexibility for data consumers through EDDK's multi-dataset export functionality. The combination of DuckDB-based vectorised processing, TimescaleDB for intermediate staging, and MQTT streaming for publication proved effective for handling this data volume on a single server. All dataset inventories, metadata, and structural information are consolidated in the accompanying Excel workbook, providing a comprehensive reference for anyone accessing the data on EDDK.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

The infrastructure presented in this deliverable demonstrates a modular design that balances the needs of the current prototyping phase against future scalability. A key strength is that the ingest adapter is source-agnostic: it reads from the local file system during prototyping, but can just as easily be configured to ingest data directly from EDDK or other secure storage solutions once they are in use. Combined with the deliberate split between relational storage for topology and object storage for timeseries, this ensures the infrastructure is future-proof, compliant with data governance requirements, and adaptable to different phases of the project.

Future extensions will focus on scalability, flexibility, and long-term data governance:

- **Optimised partitioning and sharding:** refine the existing date-based partitioning and Smart Meter ID sharding by tuning shard counts and introducing topology-based partitioning, guided by observed query patterns to further reduce processing overhead on the object storage layer.
- **Advanced ingestion:** extend the Airflow DAG to connect directly to external sources such as EDDK, S3, or APIs, removing the current dependency on local file delivery.
- **Data lifecycle management:** define retention, archival, and synchronisation policies between PostgreSQL, the object storage layer, and EDDK to ensure traceability and compliance.
- **Scaling strategies:** evaluate replication, sharding, and load balancing options for PostgreSQL and the object storage layer as dataset size and usage grow.

This will ensure the infrastructure evolves into a hybrid, source-agnostic architecture that can efficiently handle both operational database workloads and large-scale analytics, while remaining aligned with the Danish energy sector's data governance framework.

Appendix: Definition of terms

Alias(es)	Meaning	Named Location
<i>data app</i>	Functional data processing unit, based on configuration, input and output formats.	concept originated in project proposal
<i>data pipeline</i>	Conceptual sequence of data apps to generate insights and services	concept originated in project proposal
<i>service</i>	User-facing endpoint of a data pipeline, including a graphical user interface with functionality to query precomputed results and potentially an interaction mechanisms to configure and trigger data pipeline execution. Endpoint may have varied security privileges, including public-facing endpoints.	concept originated in project proposal
Energidata.dk (<i>EDDK</i>)	Platform to host open and protected data from the Danish energy system as well as data from several "living labs" and research projects. Here it is used to create a protected and maintainable data host.	Energidata.dk entrypoint: Dataset "3PhaseInsightProject"
<i>local prototyping environment</i>	Initial Python development platform for data apps and data pipelines, developed at DTU. It was developed to formalize the data app concept and allows rapid prototyping and HPC compatible deployment of data apps. Implemented with pure file-based data storage and access. No data-versioning.	Contact DTU authors for access.
<i>cloud-compatible platform</i>	A cloud-compatible open-source platform developed by INILAB to enable professional and scalable data handling and deployment of data apps, comprising the 3PhaseInsight <i>framework</i> (<i>3phi-framework</i>) and the <i>data platform</i> .	3PhaseInsight at GitHub
3PhaseInsight <i>framework</i>	The core interoperable data app framework, which defines the core libraries and connectors and contains the code for available data apps. provides REST endpoints	3phi-framework
<i>data platform</i>	An open-source modular platform containing necessary components to spin off functionalities given by the <i>framework</i>	data-platform
<i>DAG</i>	A workflow definition that specifies a set of tasks and their dependencies, providing the mechanism to schedule, trigger and monitor the execution of one or more Data Apps within the platform. A DAG can specify a single Data App or a entire data pipeline.	part of data-platform
<i>endpoint, API</i>	A single addressable route on the platform's HTTP API through which an external consumer retrieves a specific Data App's results over standard HTTP. The API itself is FastAPI application that serves as the single egress point through which external consumers query Data App results.	data-platform-api, part of data-platform
API	Customer-facing HTTP API for the 3PhaseInsight Data Platform.	data-platform-api, part of data-platform

Table 3: Terminology mapping. Preferred aliases are shown in italics.

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